

REENGINEERING THE NIGERIAN TOURISM INDUSTRY FOR SUSTAINABILITY: THE SYSTEMIC OPERATIONS MANAGEMENT PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

The Nigerian tourism industry boasts of potentials that when explored can boost socio-economic activities to enviable heights. Nevertheless, obvious challenges and vicissitudes that characterize the industry have left it operating below expectation. This study x-rayed how the industry can be reengineered for sustainability based on the systemic operations management perspective. The tenets of tourism and sustainable tourism were richly explored; while reengineering processes and implications of the systemic operations management perspective were highlighted. The main cause of the continuous underdevelopment of Nigerian tourism industry is the lack of investment in the sector. Government and private investors (domestic and foreign) are very limited in their investment drive due to some predicaments. Based on the findings, the study concluded that the rich tourism benefits in Nigeria and its capabilities to drastically reduce poverty, aid economic diversification (which is predominated by oil), employment generation, revenue redistribution and environmental sustainability are yet to be realized as the potentials of tourism remain largely untapped. In spite of these challenges, the application of the reengineering process, anchored on systemic operations management can proffer lasting solutions.

KEYWORDS

Economic Diversification, Employment Generation, Environmental Sustainability, General System Concept, Sustainable Tourism, Systemic Model.

INTRODUCTION

Tourism has been defined as a form of recreation which involves overnight travel or stay of a certain distance away from one's usual abode in search of relaxation, excitement, and cure for various health challenges (Njoku, 2003). Its activity outcomes can be measured with many critical economic metrics (wealth creation, employment generation, and foreign earnings); yet it is very well regarded as the origin of too many issues when related to sustainable development. A major challenge facing tourism development globally is how to succeed with the potentials of tourism and still preserve the environment as well as tradition and cultural multiplicity. It is a truism that tourism is predominantly advancing the economies of many countries; especially, the developed economies. In Africa for instance, the sector registered only 5% of international tourist arrivals and 3% of incomes in 2016 (United Nations World Tourism Organization [UNWTO] 2017, p. 1) and this status seem to have declined in recent times; no thanks to the Covid-19 pandemic which halted tourism activities in year 2020. In spite of this, a rebound in upward trend is expected; and that should encourage countries, public and private investors as well as companies to inquire more about the potentials of tourism development.

The concept of sustainability in tourism, highlights the importance of tourism development that meets the need of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meeting their own needs (United Nations World Commission on the Environment and Development [UNWCED], 1987, p. 42). In the words of Tosun (1998, p. 596), it entails all forms of tourism developments that make notable contributions to, or at least, do not oppose the indefinite maintenance of development principles without jeopardizing or compromising the ability of coming generations to meeting their own needs and desires.

Reengineering on the other hand, requires a fundamental rethinking and radical redesign of business processes so as to accomplish improvements of significant and dramatic nature in critical and contemporary measures of performance like cost, quality, and service and speed (Hammer & Champy, 1993). In other words, reengineering processes help organizations to achieve their goals and objectives through radical process change or redesign (Ndu&Obiora, 2015). The state of the Nigerian tourism industry is such that it is rich in potentials but grossly lacking in development; albeit, the sustainable form. Government efforts have at best remained bureaucratic, marred with political party's idiosyncratic ideology and at best unsustainable; as successive administrations jettison the efforts of past ones to pursue newer ones. This 'rat race' has continued over the years; leaving the Nigerian tourism industry in state of dire need for radical and sustainable redesigning. This paper therefore, is an attempt at proffering a lasting solution to this menace, using the systemic operations management approach; which seeks to holistically integrate relevant systems and resources (human and material) in the tourism value creation process. In doing this, the concept of sustainable tourism was x-rayed, the history and challenges of the Nigerian tourism industry chronicled and reengineering process reviewed in the light of systemic operations management of the Nigerian tourism industry; with conclusions drawn and relevant solutions advocated.

The Concept of Tourism and its Benefits

Tourism is the "set of activities of a person travelling to a place outside his/her usual environment for less than a year and whose main purpose of travel is other than the exercise of an activity remunerated from within the place visited" (United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural

Organization [UNESCO], 2000). In line with Njoku (2003), it comprises the activities of people travelling to and staying in places outside their usual environments for not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes. Tourism undoubtedly has enormous economic influence on almost every area of the society owing to its rapid growth, acceptance and view as the game changer industry globally (Aliyu, Abdulkadir & Aliyu, 2013). The potentials and impact of tourism can be felt in its ability to reduce and alleviate poverty, create jobs as well as redistribute income in local communities. Given the market competition in the tourism industry, government and private entrepreneurs are beginning to maximize the prospects of attracting foreign tourists to their countries. To take advantage of these abundant abilities that are resident in tourism industry, countries have started to position their regions, cities and states in a tourism-like manner so as to attract tourists and tourist investments (Gil & Ritchie, 2008). Tourism as an alternate revenue generating source is the new approach in most countries due to its multiplier effect on other sections of the economy, creating large volume of job for both skilled and unskilled labor (Ayeni & Eboho, 2013). Basically, the impressions of tourism are felt in a nation socially, environmentally and economically. At the societal level, the benefits cut across peasants, artisans and even professionals irrespective of gender, race or age bracket. Environmentally, tourism has the potentials to conserve the natural environment, preserve antiquities, historical monuments and traditional behaviours such as culture, food, language, heritage, arts and crafts. While economically, tourism creates wealth capable of stimulating both domestic and foreign earnings of any nation from direct activities or associated businesses (Government of Federal Republic of Nigeria [FGN], 2006).

Brief History of Tourism in Nigeria: Prospects and Challenges

Nigeria is blessed with material, human and natural resources such as solid minerals, crude oil deposits and natural gas with an estimated population of about 160 million people (according to 2006 census figure). Ironically, the riches do not transform to better life for the citizens as standard of living in Nigeria is below the United Nation's benchmark, life expectancy is also low, poverty, diseases and illiteracy level is on the high side. Meaning that, Nigeria is a rich country with poor people (APRM, 2008). Nigeria is a multi-ethnic state endeared with rich cultures; incidentally the major cultures seem to be decimated by geographic boundaries, giving birth to distinct cultures between the 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory (Bola, 2010; Samuel, 2010). Although leisure and tourism activities in Nigeria began since the colonial era and continued till independence in 1960, the government got involved in tourism by setting up national tourism board in the year in 1976 and in 1990, the first tourism policy was formulated and adopted (Bola, 2010). During the military rule, tourism was not developed and was not in the plan until the return to civil rule through democracy in 1999 during the administration of General Olusegun Obasanjo. His administration orchestrated the industry and saw it as an economic strategy for economic diversification. By this, National Tourism Development Board [NTDB] established in 1992 was rejuvenated. The agency was given the mandate to register and classify all hospitality organizations and to ensure that they adhere to international standard and practices, engage in destination promotion activities both within the local and international space. In 2005 the ministry of culture and tourism as a way of promotional activities organized the first ever Abuja carnival while in 2006, UNWTO and UNESCO prepared a comprehensive tourism development master plan.

Tourism prospects in Nigeria are quite positive with lots of potentialities. It features a country that is privileged and blessed in terms of natural attractions amongst many African countries. These

attractions are not limited to only mountains, hills and highlands; caves and valleys (with waterfalls and water tributaries); wonderful vegetation (dense high forest, savannah and Sahel); numerous species of wildlife, flora and fauna. These tourism assets are enormously great and assorted with capacity for economic revolutions, diversification, poverty reduction, income redeployments and foreign direct investments. Community participation and sustainability programmes to a very large extent determine the degree to which these potentials are harnessed (Hall, 2007). According to UNWTO (2011), tourism offers communities the opportunities to gain from their cultural and natural assets through the creation of employment in tourism related activities and the supply of services and goods such as food, excursions or handicrafts, to tourism businesses or directly to visitors, without having to leave to towns in search of a better life (UNWTO, 2011).

In terms of the challenges, Nigeria is among the league of countries that have not optimized and maximized her tourism potentials and this is related to government's lack of commitment in providing a safe and conducive social cum economic environment, as well as the required infrastructure to drive tourism development. The inadequacy and absence of this infrastructure is worst hit in the rural areas where natural land formations and attractive tourist's sites are situated. The concentration of past and present government on urbanization has significantly rendered efforts to develop tourism supportive infrastructures very insignificant (Briedenhann & Wickens, 2004). According to Fayissa, Nsiah and Tadaese, (2007), developmental efforts should be concentrated on the locations where these tourism potentials are so as to bring about economic value that will better the economic lives of the communities. In order to positively optimize and maximize all the economic benefits of tourism, all leakages and wastages should be tackled intentionally and to achieve that, local patronage of food, drinks, souvenirs, manpower and even facilities at the site should be encouraged (Felix & Usman, 2008). Nigeria's tourism potentials can only be utilized sustainably, if there are policy makers, private investors who will develop both patriotic and political will in terms of systematic collaboration, partnership in providing adequate security, building roads, airports, electricity, telecommunication and even internet facilities linking the sites. Also, there is the need to have a comprehensive tourism arrival data base so as to encourage active private participation in areas such as hotel accommodation, transportation and tour guide activities (Eja, Oto, Yaro, & Inyang, 2011).

In spite of her unique opportunities for pleasurable attractions, these challenges have made Nigeria not to be a choice destination for most inbound tourists even with venture and fun-seeking individuals. The reasons are related to security challenges, little or no tourism structure, political unsteadiness and a host of other challenges. Most international arrivals in Nigeria are business related and not tourism related. Yet there is no precise statistically verified data of definite number of visitors and their purpose of visit to Nigeria. UNWTO have promoted the creation of tourism satellite account (TSA) so as to measure the monetary influence and contributions to GDP arising from both domestic and international visits in tourism sector of any country. Moreover, domestic tourism that will compliment international tourism is quite unimpressive, and this could be traced to low awareness and the income level of an average Nigerian who cannot afford the luxury of tourism activities due to low income (Awaritefe, 2007). Hardly do Nigerians visit any tourist destination in the country while on vacation except for seminars, conferences, meetings or political party's convention scheduled at any of the tourist attraction centres. The average Nigerian prefers to visits friends and relations in their villages during festivals, ceremony or holidays while the advantaged government officials travel

to more tourism developed countries for vacation and medical tourism which affect domestic contribution to tourism earnings (Awaritefe, 2004).

Sustainable Tourism and the Pillars of Sustainable Development

Sustainable tourism as stated earlier, is that which meets the tourism needs of a people without jeopardizing or compromising the ability of future generations to meeting theirs. It responds to the need of tourists, industry and local communities by taking into account the present and future impacts of tourism with regard to the environmental, social and economic perspectives (Minciu, Popesu, Padurean, Hornoiu, & Baltaretu, 2010, p. 85). Considering these facts, it becomes instinctively doubtful that tourism benefits would include the overall philosophies of sustainable development (Castellani & Sala, 2010; Hunter, 1997; Tao & Wall, 2009). For instance, tourism brings together some strategic and marketing attentions which relegates reflections on environmental conservation cum preservation and further disregard social and environmental preoccupation over the long term. However, the place of sustainable development in the tourism industry is likely to be strengthened due to political and media attentions as well as increasing awareness of the tourists themselves.

Sustainable development is a current look resulting from the interest with which the current generations are thinking about the next generations. As far as regional development is concerned, it suggests a reflection of long-term effects of recycling uninhibited spaces and renewing the degraded areas. The concept of sustainable development in general is the creation of a non-temporary balance amongst natural resources and use of them by human beings. There are three categories of interest: economic, environmental and social. Sustainable development consists of a group of resources (air, water, welfare, culture, nature, money, etc.) which are all very vital. The goal of sustainable development is to successfully resolve between economic growth, admiration of the environment and social progress. In an economic sense, sustainable development chases growth; a fruitful globalization that endorses cooperation among firms, institutions and public authorities. Anywell-organized economy forsakes the use of unmaintainable production systems. The principle of polluter/payer is a case in point. In terms environment, the goal is to preserve and protect the natural environment by reducing greenhouse gas emissions, pollution of air and water through recycling and putting every energy to avoid the extinction of plant and animal species, deforestation, desertification and the weakening of natural resources. At the social level, especially for the fact that earth's population has been projected to hit about ten billion by 2050 (United Nations Population Division [UNPD], 2019), sustainable development aims at providing food, water and labour for coming generations and reducing disparities among people groups. It was also stated on principles and ideologies like unity and equity for the present and the future generations in order to bring about a significant development in the welfare of each individual in terms of health, education, and well-being. Moreover, sustainable development is armed with the objective of preserving local traditions and authenticity while promoting the development of populations. The main principles of sustainable tourism as advocated by White, McCrum, Blackstock and Scott (2006), have been captured in figure 1.

Figure 1: Principles of Sustainable Tourism
 Source: Adopted from White, et al (2006).

Figure 1 shows the three main dimensions of sustainable tourism (socio-cultural, environmental and economic dimensions) with their associated principles. Socio-cultural has seven; environmental has five principles while economic has six. These principles are the yardstick for measuring the effectiveness of a sustainable tourism effort.

Concept of Reengineering and Tourism Reengineering for Sustainability

Reengineering is the rapid, radical redesign of strategic, value-added business processes and the classifications, strategies and organizational structures that support them to improve the work movements and productivity in an organization (Manganelli & Klein, 1994). Hammer and Champy (1993) defined reengineering as the fundamental rethinking and radical redesign and restructuring of business module to achieve better improvements in critical, contemporary indicators of performance such as cost, quality, service and speed. Although reengineering may not be too different from business processes like total quality management and lean manufacturing, the need to reengineer in response to increase in e-commerce, places firms under pressure to reform their businesses. Nevertheless, it is recommended that radical invention in innovation are not new and discoveries occur through “vision” and its ability to break boundaries of predictable thinking that had limited performance for preceding periods (Manganelli & Klein, 1994). Some of the benefits associated with reengineering include improved efficiency, increased effectiveness; cost savings, meaningful work for employees, increased flexibility and adaptability to change and business Growth (Counter, 2002;

Kapoor, 2010). Hammer and Stanton (1995) suggested some skills that are required for proper reengineering process namely: process-orientation; holistic perspective; creativity; restlessness; enthusiasm; optimism; persistence; tact; team player and communication skills. The redesigning process is a procedure that provides support to the developers to find the radical factor that will bring about the competitive difference and this commences with a well thought out peculiar methodology which shows the road map that will help to get to where the industry wants to go (Manganelli & Klein, 1994). As a management concept, reengineering is not quite different from other major approaches; hence the imperativeness of planning. It will be necessary to search for a correct and exact methodology that will better fit with the reengineering process development. Manganelli and Klein (1994) state that a methodology is a systematic or clearly defined way of accomplishing an end and also a system of order in thought or action plus it must follow five subsequent stages to become a successful and an efficient methodology.

Figure 2: Reengineering Process Model

Source: Manganelli and Klein (1994) as cited in Susana (2013).

Although, the stages are designed to be performed consecutively and the reengineering process methodology can be customized to the needs of each reengineering project; hence skipping, rearranging or recombining tasks to meet individual needs (Manganelli & Klein, 1994). Nevertheless, the process must involve the redrawing in structures and processes at the technological,

organizational and human levels in order to achieve impressive performance improvements and focusing on a customer service orientation.

Reengineering Processes in Tourism

Today, many tourist destinations get to the final parts of their lifespan more quickly than ever before and that has an unbelievable implication for communal powers that be and private businesses in getting areas which forces the destinations to take pro-active measures to fortify the quality and image of the proposed services (Ioannides, 2006). Not too many tourists' destinations remain persistent and unchanging, and those that do are most likely supposed as out of date and unappealing (Butler, 2004 cited in Ioannides, 2006). So, destinations must adjust, not simply because they must renovate but because they have to hold and enhance their attractiveness over other tourist destination sites; there by necessitating frequent redesigns so as to dislodge the competition (Ioannides, 2006). In the era of "post-tourism", old tourist destinations must reorganize, modify or face deterioration, and that modification must occur at least, at three levels (Stamboulis & Skayannis, 2003):

- (1) The sensitivities of tourists (the consumers of the tourist product) changes in dissimilar directions. The larger pull of tourists still looks out to the consumption of the "4Ss", but the records of those in search of "something different" is growing.
- (2) Modification in the mode of supply of tourism locations and attractions has become glaring. Tourists learn about new destinations, amenities and activities, which ultimately become trendy, subsequently renovated, and then sell their product by themselves so as to meet or to create new tourist demand. Subsequently, they are appreciative to enter into a world of intensified competition.
- (3) There is a change in the suppliers of both the ultimate product and the transitional products in an effort to dominate new tourist product markets and customers rising from the change of the tourist business. When a destination finds it difficult maintaining its competitive advantage, in spite of having up-to-date amenities and meeting prospects of modern tourists, it has to market itself more aggressively in order to be revitalized (Weber & Tomljenovic cited in Ioannides, 2006) Competitive positioning strategies have to be developed and implemented based on tenets of flexibility, specialization and emphasis to promoting the competitive advantages of tourism destinations.

The Systemic Operations Management Perspective

Systemic operations management (SOM) entails seeing the organization as consisting of interconnected and interdependent parts that must function together as an integrated whole in a given environment to achieve a unified goal (Ndu, 2019). According to Ndu (2019), it requires operations managers to efficiently and effectively integrate organizational resources through the managerial processes of planning, organizing, directing and controlling in order to create value in form of goods and services. The reengineering process itself is a systemic model. Hence, it can only achieve its purpose when implemented in the context of the SOM perspective. This entails analysis of the structural and functional aspects of the Nigerian tourism industry; treating it as a multifaceted set of internal and external connections that must function together in order to achieve preset goals. By so doing, the systemic perspective appeals to the general system concept which is the creation of a combination between two models: the model cybernetics (contingency) and the structural model (integration of the internal functioning of the system). According to de Rosnay (1975), a system

comprises a set of essentials interfacing actively and prearranged according to specific objective(s). A system is structured into 4 parts (de Rosnay, 1975):

- Countable and more or less similar items (that's to say, assembled in groups, families or populations).
- A limit, that outlines the borderline between all fundamentals and the environment (Pollalis and Dimitriou, 2008). This limit is slightly indistinct, moving and more or less penetrable concerning tourism as a social system (Ko, 2005).
- Networks relationship between system components. The more there are interrelationships, the better the organization and the involvedness. These contacts rest generally on physical communication networks that deliver interactions of materials, electricity or information through roads, canals, electric conductors, phone wires, fiber optic etc.,
- Tanks used to stock power, materials or information (reservoirs of the atmosphere or capital reserve of knowledge, media memory, library, gas tank, etc.)

At the operational stage, a system is characterized by 4 elements too:

- Material flows, energy or information, which use networks of relationships. Material and power flows can upsurge or decline the level of tank level. While information flows act as a decision basis, they affect other types of flows to regulate tank levels,
- Decision centers, which shape the network of relationships, that's to say, they coordinate and manage the stocks.
- Delays ensuing from diverse rates of flow movement, storage capacity in reservoirs, or friction between the elements of the system. They are a fundamental feature of the behaviour of multifaceted systems through intensifying or avoiding the appearance of some spectacles.
- Feedback loops provide information on the coming impacts after the flow enters. Thus, the decision centers can have quick and fast information about the general state of the system and anticipate its evolution.

From a structural and functional point of view, this definition displays that the tourism industry, tourist resorts, and tourist organizations belong to open complex systems with intense material and information exchanges with their environment (Ko, 2005). It is very useful to understand how tourism can successfully incorporate sustainable principles. Most importantly, it highlights the possible reconciliation between sustainable development and the structure of the tourism system as well as between sustainable development and the function of the tourist system.

Systemic Reengineering for Sustainable Tourism in Nigeria

The reengineering process has been highlighted in a previous section of this work. For effective application of this systemic reengineering process, the suitability of sustainable development and the structure of the Nigerian tourism system should be re-examined; because of the necessity to regulate the extent to which sustainable development can be merged in the following tourism constituents - its frontier, its uncountable and interrelated elements and its reservoir (energy, material and information). Bearing in mind that tourism destination as a multipart social system approves that the development of a given tourism destination does not result from a simple market process. In fact, the development of a tourism destination is the outcome of agreements between numerous actors, an elusive interaction of individuals and group participants' issues. These actors look for individual interests, which are often inconsistent like exploiting profit for firms and usefulness for the people

and the decrease in unemployment rates for local authorities. Images on sustainable development should be made internal and in liaising with the whole group of participants too. They can be represented by the tourist agencies, hosting providers, carriers, restaurateurs, residents, customers, consumer organizations, legislative and political bodies, certification groups, local communities and companies. Outside the documentation of the mechanisms within the system that can contribute to sustainable development for tourism, the systems actors' (whether physical or legal element), understanding of the functioning and evolution of a system depends mainly on the kind of relationship among participants as highlighted below:

i) The Organization Conditions the Tourist Activity

Within a sustainable approach to tourism, it is of critical importance to assemble all participants and thus, all the resources and skills of tourism. The first participant is the organization which is in charge of tourism service and products. Taking control of skills and resources is essential. Within, sustainable development has to be knitted. This relationship affects all economic ventures for as long as it concerns the several services of the organization, from production to consumption.

ii) Service Providers

The relationships between tourism organizations and service providers are very central as they determine the set of services offered to tourists/visitors. A tourist attraction can be assessed in terms of its pull and this can happen through the level of cooperation between different service providers. Certainly, outside the rivalry between organizations, this rivalry is determined by the tourist destination on which firms are settled and the service package offered to meet tourists/visitors' expectations. Generally, service providers in tourism are of different types and sizes. Tour operators, transportation companies (air, sea, land), hotels, restaurants and entertainment chains which may be global in outlook and operations (for example: Thomas Cook, Air France, Accor, Disneyland). However, most service providers are SMEs operating in local transport, accommodation, catering and entertainment of tourists.

iii) Relationships with Present and Potential Tourists/Visitors (Customers)

Whether small or large, tourism organizations pursue to uphold close interactions with their clients essentially for very strategic reasons. Literature, actually, shows that customer orientation positively influences the organization's profitability and performance (Bitner, 1990; Goodale, Koener & Roney, 1997). Tourist focus or intensity of service is mainly intended at tourist/visitor satisfaction while maintaining the firm's competitiveness. This satisfaction is founded primarily on the perceived service quality and any possible nonconformity from the expected quality. The level of customers' satisfaction is very difficult to determine because, on the one hand, it depends on the inherent quality of individual and comprehensive services. In fact, the relationship between tourists and service providers directs the picture of tourism and mutual practices, especially in terms of loyalty.

iv) Public Organizations for Tourism Promotion

In a tourist site, these entities organize the vertical regulation system (the sector) seeking to promote the site. This requires some coordination between actors and especially between service providers and local authorities on the one hand; and between service providers themselves. For example, many tourist offices offer on their websites many types of accommodation for the same site as a supermarket shelf.

v) *Local Communities*

Local communities have dual goals with which they communicate on the ground of their territorial jurisdiction - citizens and companies. As citizens select representatives of these communities, the elected representatives should focus on the actual needs of citizens; though, the actualization of these objectives is dependent on the economic development of regions. Therefore, they should be more committed in their relation to local firms. Communities do provide the people with soft loans in order to make possible their access to cultural facilities, entertainment and sports as well as to finance and assist tourist organization in their local development program.

vi) *Learning Sustainable Development and its Feedback Loops*

Both learning and feedback loops are crucial elements of complex system that we are explaining for the tourist system. Sustainable development is such a complex system that requires learning and knowledge transfer. Tourist firms can depend on their preceding faults in transmitting the best actions to be undertaken in sustainable development. They also abide by the instructions of decision-makers. Learning distributes data. Marketing communication is very important and it tries to be genuine in the eyes of tourists. Sustainable development-oriented communication and activities make it possible to strengthen the links between the tourist organization and the customer who expects environmental action and to enhance its image. Feedback loops can also be used to control and evaluate the effect of tourist practices and sustainable activities on economic, social and environmental development. The systemic presentation of sustainable tourism initiatives shows that individual participation in social and ecological tourism, results from registering quickly in a complex but synergistic system.

CONCLUSIONS

This study set out to examine the Nigerian tourism industry and how it can be reengineered for sustainability based on the systemic operations perspective. The tenets of tourism and sustainable tourism were richly explored; while reengineering processes and implications of the the systemic perspective were highlighted. Based on this methodology and processing, this study aligns with Eja and Ajake (2005) to conclude that having examined the massive and rich tourism benefits in Nigeria and its capabilities to drastically reduce poverty, aid economic diversification which is predominated by oil, employment generation, revenue redistribution and environmental sustainability, the potentials of tourism remain largely untapped. The main cause of the continuous underdevelopment of Nigerian tourism industry is the lack of investment in the sector. Government and private investors (domestic and foreign) are very limited in their investment drive owing to some predicaments. These predicaments according to Aniah, (2006) are: Current Markets, Product Development Opportunities – New Markets, Tourism Development Component etc. In spite of these challenges, the application of systemic reengineering process can proffer lasting solution to these challenges.

Recommendations

Nigeria as an export driven economy is predictable to profit on a large scale from tourism connected components of international trade; while guaranteeing sustainability. However, for that to happen, application of the reengineering process anchored on systemic operations management principles need to be adopted as outlined below.

1. A tourism stakeholders meeting must be convened for at least, sensitization and mobilization purposes.
2. The target market and potential customers (which includes domestic and international tourists) must be identified *viz-à-viz* the key performance indicators (such as number of tourist arrivals, customer satisfaction levels etc.) the required work processes, needed resources (which may be human, material or infrastructural).
3. Challenges, leakages and gaps in the Nigerian tourism industry must be identified and communicated to the stakeholders. The desired state must as well be clearly defined and communicated to them. This can be achieved by benchmarking against the tourism industry of another country. The idea here is to create a vision of the desired state that must be vigorously pursued by all stakeholders. Security, infrastructural development, amenities, promotion and awareness, funding and financing, attitude and image are some of the gaps and major challenges that must be addressed for sustainable tourism development in Nigeria.
4. The needed systems and processes for mitigating these challenges must be established. It would require the establishment of standard operating procedures and control measures. It would also require the setting up of structures that would efficiently and effectively operate the system. Full commercialization of the tourism industry is advocated here. By that, the industry must be divested from political office holders such that only professionals with the requisite experience should be allowed to head and lead the industry. Investors should be encouraged with incentives like tax holidays, import duty waivers, interest free loans etc. Security challenges should be confronted head-on by government while providing the needed infrastructural development. Regulatory agencies should also live up to expectation by ensuring strict compliance to set standards.
5. These articulations must be transformed to workable process vision that must be continually reviewed based on current realities. Hence, a systemic reengineering process team should be set up to manage the process. They should be charged with the responsibility of periodically reviewing the process and making changes where necessary.

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